

Smart metering deployment status across EU-28

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Abstract—The scope of this paper is to present an EU-28 overview of the smart meter roll-out implementation progress. The study is based on publicly available information and presents a traffic light map with the deployment status by mid-2017. A series of particular cases are approached and a gap between the European Commission recommendation, expected diffusion rate and actual deployment is identified. The study further provides some possible causes considering the number of metering points available at EU-28 level, country specific assumed targets and macro-environmental factors.

Index Terms—smart metering, roll-out plan, EU-28, deployment status

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increased number of EU member states and the emergence of new technologies for energy generation and storage, the European Commission had to set up a legal framework for the harmonization and liberalization of the internal energy markets (inclusive of electricity and gas). Thus, through on Article 194 of the TFEU [1], the EU initiated Energy Packages to develop a resilient and integrated energy market across the EU. In the context of the establishment and functioning of the internal market and for the need to preserve and improve the environment, Union policy on energy shall aim, in a spirit of solidarity between Member States:

- (a) to ensure the functioning of the energy market;
- (b) to ensure security of energy supply in the Union;
- (c) to promote the energy efficiency and energy saving and the development of new and renewable forms of energy; and
- (d) to promote the interconnection of energy networks.

Directive 72 [2] adopted in 2009 with the third energy package presents common rules for the internal market in electricity and all EU member states should have transposed this Directive into national law by 3rd of March 2011.

The adoption of Directive 2009/72/EC [2] drove commercial and technical initiatives. A cost benefit analysis (CBA) was commissioned in most EU countries. Based on the results of the CBA each country has to provide a smart metering deployment strategy to achieve a minimum 80% EU recommended penetration rate by 2020. The currently expected EU-28 penetration rate is 72% by 2020 [3]. Large projects like OpenMeter (2009 - partners CEN-CENELEC-ETSI, the main European energy utilities, meter manufacturers, research institutes and universities) assessed the available technologies and provided input for a potential roll-out of smart meters throughout Europe and issued recommendations for standards which are now incorporated in Mandate 441 [4].

The European Commission ordered standard organizations to develop reference architecture to facilitate creating rules for design and analysis of Smart Grid solutions. The Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) is a representation of Smart Grid solutions and is popular among Smart Grid stakeholder (utilities and research institutes [5]). SGAM has been developed as part of the reference architecture framework specified in EU Mandate M/490 [6] to European standardization organizations to support the Smart Grid deployment. In this framework several projects received funding from EC for both research and large-scale demonstrators. Among them the inteGRIDy H2020 project is an Innovation Action aiming at demonstrating demand response, smartening the distribution grid, energy storage distribution and Smart Grid transport integration in 10 pilot sites across Europe. One of the supportive tasks was to investigate the deployment status and diffusion rate of electrical energy smart metering alongside with the regulation consistency and other external factors. The outcome of this task is a public report *Smart Grid Deployment, Infrastructures & Industrial Policy applicable to the inteGRIDy pilot cases* [7].

Extending a little bit, the range of this study the communication remains Achilles' heel in smart grid topologies deployed worldwide. The identification of suitable communication protocols and cost-effective network architectures represent a challenging aspect and wireless networks are investigated in [8]. Outside Europe government and competent scientific institutes make efforts to ensure availability of recommendation, best practices or specific regulation to support the development of new retail services and products.

The rest of this paper is structured in four main parts as follows. Section 2 delivers an overview of the inteGRIDy project together with some details of the Romanian demonstrator. Section 3 presents the roll-out strategy across EU-28 in term of cost-benefit analysis and governmental decisions, while Section 4 provides an assessment of the deployment status in mid-2017. Finally, in Section 5 the progress of each country is compared with EC's expected diffusion rate.

II. INTEGRIDY PROJECT

inteGRIDy project is a four-year project funded by the European Commission as part of the low carbon emission initiative *Demonstration of smart grid, storage, and system integration technologies with increasing share of renewable*. The goal of the project is to facilitate the optimal and dynamic

operation of the power distribution network, boosting network stability while coordinating the inclusion of distributed energy sources, virtual power generation plants and innovative and collaborative energy storage schemes, with an increasing percentage of renewable energies [8].

Atos Spain leads a 30 partners Consortium from eight European countries: Spain, United Kingdom, Italy, Portugal, Greece, France, Romania and Cyprus.

The technical solutions proposed in inteGRIDy incorporate predictive algorithms to manage energy generation and demand as part of the 10 pilots rolled-out in 8 European Union countries. Based on pilot results, the project will propose new consistent business models with the energy paradigm proposed by inteGRIDy.

Fig. 1. Ploiesti Pilot use case

The Romanian Pilot (Fig.1) will be deployed in Ploiesti, aiming at ensuring a Demand Response (DR) system where building energy management and control systems can operate based on critical peak pricing or other DR programs that could be implemented as part of the Energy Integrated Information System (EIIS).

Fig. 2. Conceptual view of EIIS architectural design

The expected outcomes include monitoring and control of the operation of DR programmes in order to decrease the peak of power consumption, engaging consumers in DR, testing

and validating the concept of a Distribution System Operator (DSO) as a user of demand-side flexibility.

Moreover, the consumer behaviour will be analysed to increase flexibility of energy consumption using specific DR intelligent algorithms with the final goal of providing trade flexibility solutions.

On a technical perspective the Romanian pilot has the major functional components are presented in (Fig. 2) as architectural layers: data collection; data processing and data presentation.

On the operational level, EIIS implements two DR use cases, one for eight residential users and another one for two office buildings. The information is collected from smart meters and sensors (smart plugs, HVAC, temperature). Home appliances will be monitored with smart plugs and each consumer will be identified for an accurate DR engagement.

Based on the two prospects mentioned above Ploiesti Pilot aims at implementing the EIIS, a solution to automate the process of DR based on smart meters infrastructure and optimizing the process workflow from the data collection and metering to data processing based on DR methods and algorithms.

The core integration platform will handle several DR profiles, which could then be tested. Such an implementation could then serve as a main starting point for latter more complex DR profiles, like Demand Side Management (DSM) and bring elements of automated decision-making, based on various profiles or criteria.

Following a cross-evaluation of inteGRIDy pilots, the identified technological barriers are not supposed to be a critical bound because technological solutions are available, but the regulatory framework results to be a cornerstone problem that could affect an effective development of Demand Response approaches and the deployment and exploitation of energy storage technologies.

From such perspective, inteGRIDy and similar projects are just in-time and the pilot tests will provide real life data and results that will be useful to policymakers and stakeholders to manage and regulate the evolution processes.

III. EU-28 ROLL-OUT STRATEGY

The roll-out strategy across EU-28 relies on both the European context (general regulatory framework, technological advancements, etc) and country specific indicators (national laws and regulations, Gross Domestic Product, investment priorities, DSO particularities and other social aspects).

National environment (laws, rules and regulations) caused the EU smart meter roll-out across Europe to accelerate towards the 2020 targets. The first step that EU member states have to take according to Directive 72 / 2009 (in force) [2] is to commission a CBA to assess the feasibility of a smart meter national wide scale roll-out by 2020. Most of the EU-28 countries issued a cost benefit analysis.

In this study several aspects were considered for each EU member state: cost benefit analysis results, roll-out strategy, roll-out deployment plan and assumed diffusion rate. A

snapshot of the results is presented in Table 1 following the four perspectives together with some peculiarities.

TABLE 1. PROGRESS UPDATE PER EACH EU MEMBER STATE

CBA outcome	Positive	Austria, Cyprus, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Slovenia, Sweden, United Kingdom
	Negative	Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Slovakia,
	Inconclusive	Belgium, Portugal
	No CBA	Bulgaria, Croatia, Spain
Roll-out strategy	Mandatory	Austria, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Poland, Romania, Spain, United Kingdom
	Mandatory with opt-out	The Netherlands
	Voluntary	Malta, Sweden
	No governmental involvement	Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia
Roll-out deployment plan	Wide-scale (>80%)	Austria, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Malta, The Netherlands, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom
	Selective	Germany, Latvia, Slovakia
	No wide scale	Belgium, Czech Republic, Lithuania, Portugal
	No decision	Bulgaria, Cyprus, Hungary, Slovenia
	Pending approval	Romania, Poland
	New EU member state	Croatia
Assumed diffusion rate	100%	Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Ireland, Malta, The Netherlands, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom
	99%	Italy
	95%	France, Luxembourg
	80%	Austria, Greece, Poland, Romania
	23%	Germany, Latvia, Slovakia
	1%	Czech Republic
N/A	Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Hungary, Lithuania, Portugal, Slovenia	

For half of the EU member states the outcome of the CBA was positive and consequently the roll-out decision was mandatory with a high assumed diffusion rate. However every country represents a particular case. In the following paragraphs some examples are provided.

Spain did not commission a CBA, but the deployment strategy for smart meters is mandatory and the country is proceeding with a full roll-out of electricity metering in compliance with [10]. Spain started the deployment of smart meters (via DSO) in 2011 and aims at a full coverage in 2018. By mid-2017, 77% of the metering points are equipped with smart meters.

Portugal has no legal framework for a mandatory roll-out, but the largest DSO (99% of market share) decided to deploy smart meters through large pilot projects. Portugal has 17% coverage of smart metering points by August 2017 without committing to the 80% target suggested by EC.

Belgium commissioned region-specific CBAs and the outcome was inconclusive for Flanders, negative for Brussels

and had mixed results for Wallonia. Belgium is not legally bound to have 80% smart meters installed in all households and decided not to proceed with the wide-scale roll-out of smart meters in the electricity and gas markets until 2020 [11].

Romania has started the deployment of smart meters but was delayed by the National Plan of Smart Meter Implementation that is still waiting an approval from National Regulator. However, the full market liberalization (1st of January 2018) persuaded the DSOs to start large scale deployments. Poland has a similar situation.

A small group of countries decided for selective roll-outs. With a negative CBA outcome [12], Germany did not commit to a national roll-out strategy. The countries' approach is unique, and attention must be paid to the details of the deployment strategy selective with a tiered installation schedule. Germany started the roll-out of smart meters in the beginning of 2017. With a competitive market and independent regions, the German Government let the metering market self-regulate, and roll-out progresses naturally. A new law finally starts the formal roll-out of 'smart meters' and connected infrastructure in Germany and defines future roles and tasks for all market participants [13].

Croatia is a new member of the European Union and plans for a CBA. Despite an unclear legal framework, the sole distributor and single utility (HEP Group) has initiated some projects to deploy smart meters.

Non-EU countries are also considering smart metering strategies in the context of environmental sustainability of electric power generation. For instance, Switzerland has defined a "sunshine regulation" to ameliorate the cost + regulation and increasing the efficiency of DSOs, especially when combined with a credible threat of penalties. [14]

IV. EU-28 ROLL-OUT PROGRESS MID-2017

A second perspective of the study focused on the EU-28 smart metering roll-out progress in mid-2017. The results were consolidated using the traffic light method. The following parameters have been used to categorize smart meter roll-out in member states: percentage coverage with smart meters in mid-2017, prognosis for 2020 (EU expected diffusion), assumed targets (EU member states reporting on the smart metering progress in own countries), reported results of each EU member states to EC.

These parameters are consolidated in a 3+1 distribution of the EU member states.

The green category presents the EU member states that have fulfilled roll-out of smart meters or are close to complete it and countries with a coherent approach in terms of legislation, political will, stakeholders' involvement, energy market and technological aspects.

The yellow category presents the EU member states with consistent progress in smart metering and shows countries where smart meter deployment had a slow start as macro factors such as legislation, political will, market strategies and technological aspects hindered progress.

The red category presents the EU member states with small

or no progress in smart metering and shows countries in which non-alignment of political and legislative approach is blocking progress. Consumer resistance (previous political/social experiences opposing measure and monitoring systems) is considerable.

An addition category (purple) presents the EU member states with an unpredictable progress and approach of smart metering and shows those countries in which the government took a 'hands-off' position.

Fig. 3. Smart metering progress across EU-28 [7]

Considering overall progress, (Fig. 3) most of the countries assuming 100% installation rate of smart meters are most likely to achieve their target except for The Netherlands and UK. The Netherlands has achieved little progress to date and is most likely to miss the target. A unique situation has arisen in which, following a public debate on data privacy and security, it was decided to allow consumers to refuse a smart meter. The DSO is committed to offering smart meters to all consumers, the consumer can refuse or turn it 'administratively off' (opt-out). [15]

Italy completed a full roll-out in 2011 and is now working on replacing the smart meters with new generation ones. By the end of 2017, the plan to replace of first generation smart meters with second generation devices by e-distribution is envisaged. The target is to install about 35.9 million of new smart meters by 2031.

United Kingdom is one of the three EU member states alongside Germany and Finland with a competitive metering market (as opposed to a regulated metering market elsewhere). The current expectation in UK is that by the end of 2020, around 53 million smart meters will be fitted in more than 30 million premises (households and businesses) across Wales, Scotland and England. In mid-2017 England had a 24%

penetration rate.

United Kingdom is also facing challenges to replace the old smart meters to meet technical requirements. UK is the first EU member state to consider the ability to change suppliers without changing meters. The main advantage of SMETS 2 meters is that they do not lock in a particular supplier; they can be used in 'smart mode' if suppliers are switched. The SMETS 1 meters revert to dumb meters if suppliers are changed. The rollout SMETS 2 meters is dependent on the Data Communications Company (DCC) which supplies the relevant IT infrastructure which was launched at the end of 2016. Significant progress was made during the year of 2017 [16]. Continued regulatory support, and consumer uptake will drive suppliers to integrate updates in technology. It is likely that smart meter deployment will grow after 2020 until the market is saturated in 2022 [17].

Fig. 4. EU-28 progress and assumed targets until 2020

Sweden is the first EU member states to complete a full roll-out of smart meters in 2009 with enabling remote readings. By 2009, Swedish DSOs were obliged to provide monthly meter readings to each household and hourly reading to commercial and industrial customers [18]. Sweden is also the first country to report customer benefits and its current

challenge is to persuade all suppliers to offer hourly tariffs.

As part of the Nordic Imbalance Settlement (NBS) alongside with Finland and Norway, Sweden is part of a competitive end user market. Here, the meter data is also used to calculate technical network losses. The Finnish regulation enforces companies to purchase network losses from the competed markets, so the accurate loss history data is essential for purchasing [19].

Malta deployed smart meters throughout the country between 2009 and 2014. Enemalta is the sole Distribution System Operator (DSO) and energy supplier in Malta. With only one active power station at Delimara, Malta is an exceptional case of an EU member state with no energy competitive market that is not challenged by the EC.

In France by mid-2017 ENEDIS has installed smart meters to 5 million clients (14%) and started an aggressive installation with a speed of 20.000 meters installed each day. As France intends to maintain the same deployment speed their progress may be considered consistent

Looking at the technological factor the maturity level of smart metering solutions is of utmost importance and reflecting the success rate of deployment. But there are also exceptional cases. For instance, the smart metering architecture in place in Italy does not meet the minimum requirement considering readings 15' readings resolution. But we need to keep in mind that Italy was one of Europe's forerunners in implementing smart metering systems (with 95% coverage in 2011) and is now deploying 2nd generation smart meters.

V. EU-28 ROLL-OUT PROGRESS

The last layer of the study compares the EC recommendation of 80% diffusion rate achievement by 2020 with the consolidated assumed targets by the EU member states and the actual deployment in mid-2017. The consolidated estimations take into account the number of available metering points in each EU member state while in the case of the deployment status only publicly available information is considered. Table 1 shows that 12 out of 28 EU member states committed for smart meters diffusion rate under the EU expected rate estimated at 72% or have not committed at all. A gap between the EU-28 72% smart meter penetration rate expected by the European Commission and the consolidated target across all EU Member States - 56% (based on assumed targets by EU member states) was identified. Also, EU-28 diffusion of smart meters at mid-2017 is under 40% (Fig. 5) and expectations are that the process will speed up with national installation programmes.

Some of the possible causes for this gap are to be found in:

- Late approval of roll-out plans;
- Lack of legal framework in countries that decided to assume the 80% target: Romania and Poland;
- Delays in starting the deployment (latest case Ireland);
- Non-technical setbacks in France (the roll-out strategy was agreed in 2010, but the current roll-out status is one third of the 95% target assumed);

- Political and/or financial instability in Greece and Bulgaria;
- Low targets in a country with large number of metering points - Germany;
- Countries with legal framework and assumed targets but with no significant roll-out: Austria, The Netherlands, Slovakia;
- Countries with different opt-outs regulated options like the Netherlands and Austria.

Fig. 5. EU-28 smart metering progress

In conclusion it is likely that the 72% target will not be achieved by 2020. Progress is accelerating in countries with large numbers of metering points (e.g. France and United Kingdom) which have the potential to lift the overall EC penetration rate.

At global level, several countries have enacted legislation mandating adoption of smart metering networks, as part of broader clean energy initiatives. As examples in the U.S., electric utilities in 2016 had about 70 million smart metering infrastructure installations and about 88% were residential customers, making up more than half of all households in the country, in China the installed base of smart meters will grow up to 377 million units by 2020, and the Japanese TEPCO (Tokyo Electric Power Company) has announced plans to deploy 80 million smart meters over the next decade [8].

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper the results of a study that is part of the European project inteGRIDy and focused on the deployment of smart meters for electrical energy across EU member states.

The work started from former available smart metering landscapes and added new perspectives by considering not only actual deployment status but also comparing it with the assumed and recommended targets. Even more an estimated diffusion rate mid-2017 was calculated considering the estimated number of metering points in each country. This highlighted the importance of countries with large number of available metering points (Germany, France) but small progress in deploying smart meters until the date of the report. Different causes for this situation were also detailed together with country peculiarities. The findings on this study are limited to public information on smart meter deployment and to the information gathered by inteGRIDy partners.

As a conclusion, a factor that may influence the progress of smart metering installation is the consumer itself. As the consumer has access to detailed own consumption data and to price rates, it becomes aware of the available options to use electrical energy efficiently and maybe to reduce the cost of own invoice. Providing the user with data that create direct connection between own consumption and billing may encourage behavioral change and increase energy efficiency. As in some cases the political factor cannot enforce a deployment strategy, the engagement of the consumer is critical. However, consumers 'choice' does not necessarily result in rapid deployment. Thus, DSOs and suppliers are challenged to look for new and appealing strategies and design business models in order to meet the market needs and expectations.

Given the migration towards de-regulated markets, switching electricity suppliers is likely to become increasingly important to consumers. Therefore, the technology readiness level of smart meter devices and application services become one of the aspects to be immediately considered when taking large scale deployment decisions.

Beyond macro-environmental factors the DSOs seems to set the trend in the energy market. From monopolistic to competitive markets, ancillary services are not easily promoted and integrated in the energy market due to inconsistent regulations.

Modernization of energy infrastructure (smart grid) is part of the way of life technology is offering to us. Installation of smart meters puts an end to estimation billing providing a real perspective on electricity consumption in "real-time" (most of the deployed smart meters offer reading at 15 minutes interval). Precise consumption measurements, real-time meter data access and anti-fraud detection allow utilities to avoid unnecessary technical losses.

End-consumers with access to usage data are able to actively participate in conservation activities. This leads to greater environmental awareness and improves utilities' customer service. Smart meters equipped with demand response features provide consumer with the possibility to save energy during peak demand events.

This study opens new perspectives concerning policy design specific consumers based on the behavioral patterns. Thus, system monitoring, timely collection of data and understanding consumer patterns makes demand forecasting an easy and transparent step in energy management processes. Moreover, accurate and constant data availability leads to environmentally friendly consumer behaviour.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 731268.

The authors would like to thank inteGRIDy Consortium partners for their meaningful contributions to the project. Special thanks also to dr. ing. Dumitru Federenciu and ing. Marian Vanatoru from ELECTRICA SA for advice and expertise.

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